

TECHNOLOGY AND PRINCIPLES OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE WITH A FOCUS ON THE PROFESSION

Xudoyberdiyeva Gulchexra Isamidinovna

Doktorant, Toshkent viloyati Chirchiq

Davlat pedagogika universiteti

Pochta: xudoyberdiyeva.gulchexra.1988@mail.ru

Introduction: *foreign language learning technology, these methods, methods, tools, it is appropriate to use modern technologies to achieve important results in the course of the lesson. It is important for the teacher to use a variety of methods when teaching a foreign language.*

Keywords: *Pedagogy, subject, procedural, skill, qualification, terminology*

Аннотация: технология обучения иностранному языку, эти приемы, приемы, средства целесообразно использовать современные технологии для достижения важных результатов в ходе урока. Для преподавателя важно использовать разнообразные методы при обучении иностранному языку.

Ключевые слова: педагогика, предмет, процессуальный, навык, квалификация, терминология.

Annotatsiya: хорижий тилини ўрганиш технологияси, бу методлар, усуллар, воситалари дарс жараёнида муҳим натижаларга эришишда замонавий технологиялардан фойдаланиш мақсадга мувофиқдир. Чет тилини ўргатишда ўқитувчи рангба- ранг методлардан фойдаланиш муҳим.

Kalit so'zlar: Pedagogika, fan, protsessual, malaka, terminologiya

Methods: As the main goal of using the concept of modernization in foreign language teaching in the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of his personality (process-related abilities) and not to acquire the skills of a certain amount of knowledge in the field of education of language

learners.

By the decision of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, including in Uzbekistan, on December 10, 2012, the Coordinating Council was established and the State University of World Languages of Uzbekistan was designated as a working body. As a result, national standards based on CEFR were developed and implemented, and the demand for teaching and learning a foreign language in our country increased even more.

A new stage, a new era of teaching foreign languages has begun in our country. Their modern technology and competences determine the quality of teaching foreign languages. In the process of teaching foreign languages, the use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, and communicative media is required. New methods and requirements for teaching a foreign language in the country, assessing the knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the European Framework of Reference for Science (CEFR).

According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. Today, the demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. The role of technology in learning a foreign language is very important and it is divided into four parts (reading, writing, listening, speaking) and it helps to develop skills (reading, writing, listening and speaking). The role of modern technologies in language learning and teaching is incomparable.

In particular, there are several advantages of using information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. For example, listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning, when listening to audio, the learner pays more attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammar rules,

word combinations and meanings, and this method helps them to improve their speaking skills. In addition, the student uses modern technologies to a large extent, in this process, including using a computer, the learner develops speaking and listening comprehension skills by watching videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language.

Research

In 2001, The Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) laid the groundwork for the development of language proficiency, thereby emphasizing the skills of students in education and professional development. ESOL and CEFR standards and normative documents are being used by Cambridge University in many countries of the world to improve and develop this to meet the high quality of education. He created in the style and methods suitable for the whole world. The Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) is a decade of research designed to improve communication, and European CEFs have made significant contributions. Since its inception, the European Union has truly aimed at unification in all spheres of life. One of these goals is the introduction of the policy of multilingualism, which was aimed at creating opportunities for students to learn foreign languages of their interest in European educational institutions.

This, in turn, creates a basis for a significant expansion of the possibilities of practical use of the functional-semantic approach, which is being created on a functional-semantic basis, and meets the criteria of teaching and evaluation in all European languages. Learning and teaching different modern languages for communication developed communication in the project "learning and teaching modern languages for communication".

By 2009, there was even more emphasis on the CEFR. Initially, he considered the

theoretical and practical methodological issues of the communicative speech system. In these documents, the tests help the students in the first stage, that is, to develop language and knowledge skills that are appropriate for them. This modern test improves the candidate's oral and written knowledge skills, thereby improving the candidate's fluent speaking skills, not only oral, speaking and writing skills, but also effective in listening and reading. Research has been conducted on the appropriate criteria for each level in this information, in high-quality language use (council of Europe 2001:28-9) and development of writing skills (council of Europe 2009:187).

emphasized the evaluation criteria, in 2009 they paid great attention to improving the speaking skills of the candidates. The above-mentioned information was highlighted in the CEFR test for further development through pronunciation and phonological criteria in the assessment of the next level of speaking skills, whether the information meets the CEFR criteria.

List of references used

1. Novikov A.M. Metodologiya obrazovaniyam:<эгвес>ж2006. -488с.
2. ¹ Lomakino O.E. теория и практика проектирования методических систем обучения иностраннқм язқкам: на матер. Смановления будущего учителя иностранных языков: Автореферат... д-ра педагогич, наук.-волгоград 2002.-

44 с.

3. G.I. Khudoyberdieva .Analysis of the current state of vocational training of future teachers in a foreign language

4. G.I. Khudoyberdieva . Хорижий тилни касбга ёналтириб ўқитишнинг функционал модели

5. [<http://www.Edu.uz/ru>]